

LAVA TUBES OF MARS: LANDSCAPE STRATEGIES FOR LONG-TERM COLONIES ON THE RED PLANET

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1. Introduction: On Mars, future planetary missions might take advantage of underground caves such as lava tubes. Also present on Earth and the Moon, their existence on the Red Planet has been the subject of much research [1]. The Martian environment is characterised by extreme temperature fluctuations, radiation, micrometeorite impacts and other hazards which make its surface dangerous to inhabit. On the other hand, a colony located below ground would be protected from these conditions. Yet, these environments enjoy little consideration in the space architecture literature, when compared to the surface. It is known from historical case studies that the underground has intrigued mankind for a very long time: ancient populations of Cappadocia, Jordan and American indigenous people, such as the Anasazi [2], had settled there in order to protect themselves from the climate and invaders. Also, contemporary examples such as the cities of Montreal and Helsinki, show a renewed interest for this realm, moving some of their functions in the underground, such as storage, industrial facilities, gyms and swimming pools [3]. In this regard, the experience of the artist and architect César Manrique in Lanzarote is particularly significant. In his work *“Los Jameos del Agua”*, he focused on the adaptation of a lava cave, taking into consideration its habitability and the relationship between the Man and its natural environment, with the creation of a new and unveiled landscape. The present study aims to reinterpret these Terrestrial experiences, in order to offer lava underground conduits as a beneficial location for the establishment of long term colonies on the Red Planet.

2. Research Objectives: in order to be able to begin with design considerations and test possible habitability solutions, it was necessary to identify a possible case study and verify the availability of useful native assets at its location. For this scope, an extensive analysis was conducted both on lava tubes and Martian resources.

2.1 Lava tubes of Mars: because of its past volcanic activity, the Red Planet presents a wide variety of caves [1,4]. The *“Mars Global Cave Candidate Catalogue”* or *“MGC³”*, is a comprehensive and on-going catalogue of these items, which has been curated and elaborated by the USGS scientist Glen E. Cushing and his team. Starting from the database, it was possible to search for specific features which are known on Earth to be related to lava tubes: the *“skylights”*, which are local collapses of the conduit’s roof, visible from the surface. The majority of these items have been observed in an area located N/W of Arsia Mons, in the Tharsis Region (fig.1).

Fig.1) Skylights in the MGC³ plotted upon MOLA colored elevation map, (460m/ pixel).

In order to search for a significant case study, a mapping of the observable lava tubes in the area was conducted through the planetary GIS *“JMARS”*, following criteria such as the observable Sinuous Rilles and the presence of skylights. The measurements tools for the software also allowed to make some rough estimations and speculations regarding their possible interior widths, impossible to know from the surface. One significant lava tube, which had also been observed in precedent studies [4], was selected, due to its visible path and number of skylights. A segment of it was chosen as the possible location for the colony proposal of the present study (fig.2).

Fig.2) Selected site for the development of the colony (MOLA Shaded Relief NW 460 m/pixel, colored by the author).

2.2 Resources: due to the distance between Earth and Mars, a colony on the Red Planet would necessitate to be mostly self sufficient through the utilisation of local resources [5,6]. This paradigm, introduced by NASA, is known as *“In Situ Resources Utilisation”* or *“ISRU”*. To do so, local assets can be assessed and acquired, as proposed in the *“Space Mining Cycle”* [6,7], to be then transformed, through defined processes, into products for the settlement. Previous research proposed that the primary resources requirements, to enable human life on another planet, are: water, air, food, fuel, metals, plastics, power [6]. All of these assets are either

available on the planet or can be produced from local reservoirs. For this reason, a survey was conducted, on a global scale, to map their distribution and confirm their local availability at the chosen location of the colony.

2.3 Strategy: once a lava tube segment was selected and the local availability of resources confirmed, it was possible to start thinking about its strategical development. The process would comprehend a first step of further exploration with a local robotic mission, in order to confirm its true internal dimensions, and a second one, during which the interior would be adapted, in order to be compatible with its exploitation as the setting of a colony. During this second phase, tunnels providing a reliable connection between the surface and the lava tube interior would also be created and the resulting rocky materials would be used as construction material, along with regolith, for additive manufacturing. The proposed scenario, would be realised by a robotic swarm, as it would allow the process to be highly autonomous [8].

3. Results & Discussion: after the preparatory processes described previously, the colony development would be carried out in four different and modular phases. As anticipated in the paragraph 1, the surface of Mars is a dangerous environment, so only facilities that would not require a stable human presence would be established, such as: landing areas, ISRU factories, Cupolas and the power production area (fig.3). On the other hand, the habitat, along with the functions which require a stable human presence, would be positioned underground, safe from all those hazardous conditions.

Fig.3) Rendering of the surface development of the colony: at the center of the image can be seen the cupolas and the ISRU factories; on the left the production area and in the background the landing area.

3.1 Underground development: to achieve a friendly and healthy environment, the design of the habitat was driven by two factors, evidenced as fundamental to achieve well-being in confined spaces on Earth [3]: 1. Natural illumination & contact with the outside; 2. Nature (fig.4).

For these reasons, the various activities of the habitat, were located along the tube depending on their natural illumination requirements [3]: housing units, parks and farms, were located closer to the skylights, the most illuminated areas, while the other activities, such as gyms, ambulatories, offices, laboratories, etc., were located into terraced buildings placed in the darker areas

of the tube. Inspired by the Indonesian rice paddies, these buildings were designed to provide connection between the different zones of the tube, which might have different heights, but also to provide additional green and public space. In order to locate the habitations around the skylight, and leave the tube free for circulation, it is proposed to excavate them inside the lateral walls of the tube, through an optimized process. Also, under each skylight, special infrastructures called “Trees of Light” would be located. These structures were designed to be composed of three different parts: on the top, a cupola, would seal the underground environment and filter the Martian atmosphere, providing a breathable air mix and pressurizing the conduit, thanks to an integrated “MOXIE”[9] technology; in the middle, an aeroponic vertical farm, modelled after the “EDEN ISS” space greenhouse simulator data [10] and at its base a park for gathering, sports, leisure time.

Fig.4) Rendering of the underground development of the colony: a view from the top of one terraced building. At the center, the Tree of Light and the habitation systems.

4. Conclusions: the aim of this study is to propose lava tubes not only as a shelter, but as a proper landscape which can be adapted to become a suitable environment for long term living. It is thought that this kind of approach towards the design of the underground environment, according to factors which enhance its liveability, might be beneficial both to future Martian and Lunar explorations and Terrestrial urban planning.

5. References: [1] Sauro, F. et al. (2020) ‘Lava tubes on Earth, Moon and Mars: A review on their size and morphology revealed by comparative planetology’, In: *Earth-Science Reviews* 209. [2] Bannova O. (2021) *Space Architecture: Human Habitats Beyond Planet Earth*. (1st ed.) Berlin: DOM publishers. [3] Endicott, J. et al. (2020) *Underground Cities: New Frontiers in Urban Living*. (1st ed.) Singapore: Lund Humphries. [4] Cushing, G.E. (2012) ‘Candidate cave entrances on Mars’. In: *Journal of Cave and Karst Studies* 74 (1), pp.33–47. [5] Zubrin, R.M. (1996) *The Case For Mars: The Plan to Settle the Red Planet and Why We Must*. New York: Free Press. [6] Pazar, C. C. (2020) ‘Resource Utilization on Mars’, In: *The 23rd Annual International Mars Society Convention*. Online, 15-18/10/2020. At: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344326060_Resource_Utilization_on_Mars (Accessed 23/10/2021). [7] Sanders, G.B., Larson, W.E. (2011) ‘Integration of In-Situ Resource Utilization into lunar/Mars exploration through field analogs’ In: *Advances in Space Research* 47, pp.20–29. [8] Bier, H. et al. (2021) Design-to-Robotic-Production of Underground Habitats on Mars, arXiv:2105.02619. [9] Hoffman, J. et al (2021) ‘Mars Oxygen ISRU Experiment (MOXIE)’. In: *Space Science Reviews* 217(1) [10] Zabel, P. et al. (2019) ‘Crewtime in a Space Greenhouse based on the Operation of the EDEN ISS Greenhouse in Antarctica’. In: *49th International Conference on Environmental Systems*. Boston, MA, 2019, 07-11 July.